

**DEVIANT BEHAVIOR OF THE SOCIAL PROBLEMS OF MODERN
SOCIETY**

Abdusalomova Sitora Abdulloevna

The SamSU of the Faculty
Psychology and socio-political sciences
Sitoraabdusalomova3@gmail.com

Abstract: This article enlightens the issue of deviant behavior, relevance in modern society and types of diagnostic process, emotional and volitional disorders in the development of a teenager's personality, set diagnostic goals and plan a consistent system of correctional and educational work that takes into account the individual characteristics of the pupil.

Key words: Social norm behavior, deviant behavior, deviations in behavior, deviance, temporary changes, society, pre-deviant syndrome, social inequality, immoral act, drug addiction, alcoholism

In this article, the question of deviant behavior is enlightened, relevance in modern society Deviant behavior is behavior in which there is some kind of deviation in behavior from generally accepted norms in society or in certain communities.

The study of behavioral abnormalities has a long history. Even Diogenes (412-323 BC) was interested in the behavioral aspect (in the life of people), he claimed: «If someone walks around the streets and points at everything with his middle finger, they will think that he has gone mad, and if – with his index finger, then not»[1]. From this it can be seen that even in those days, human behavior, in society, was given great importance. It shows how important it is for a person to observe those rules and norms established by a certain society in a certain period of time.

Studying the concept of «deviant behavior», it is impossible not to mention, first of all, the point of view of Ya.I. Gilinsky, who considered deviation from the position of social norms, while noting that «a social norm is a historically established limit in a

particular society, a measure of permissible behavior.» Accordingly, deviance is defined as «conformity or non-conformity of actions with social norms (expectations)».[3] Deviant behavior is a stable behavior of a person that deviates from the generally accepted, most common and well—established social norms. Negative deviant behavior leads to the application of certain formal and informal sanctions by society. However, it is worth mentioning that at different times social norms of morality have different standards. Temporary changes take place, for example, the murder of a person. If you look from the point of view of morality, this is undoubtedly an immoral act, also from the religious interpretation is a grave sin, but if you take into account the war years, killing an enemy, that is, a person, was considered an obligatory measure of protection and in some sense a duty. Therefore, there cannot be one unambiguous interpretation of the concept, it is necessary to take into account the vital activity of a person in society during the period of time in which he lives. Deviant behavior is relative, because it is always evaluated from the point of view of the culture adopted in a particular community. Deviant behavior is most often an attempt to escape from society, to escape from life problems, to overcome a state of uncertainty and tension through certain compensatory forms. V.A. Labunskaya identifies three types of orientation of deviant behavior: selfish orientation (theft, theft, fraud, etc.); aggressive orientation (insult, hooliganism, etc.); 3 4 V l a s t 2 0 1 6 ' 1 1 socially passive orientation (drug addiction, alcoholism)[2].

In our opinion, it is also necessary to take into account in individual work the individual-personal, psychological, socio-psychological, ethnopsychological features of a difficult teenager in a multiethnic school, national traditions in the family.

The emotional and volitional disorders in the development of a teenager's personality revealed in the course of diagnosis make it possible to set diagnostic goals and plan a consistent system of correctional and educational work that takes into account the individual characteristics of the pupil.

According to Y.V. Golubev, the classification of deviant behavior of adolescents also includes various levels (types) of deviant behavior:

- criminogenic level;
- pre-criminogenic level;
- pre-deviant syndrome.

1. Pre-criminal level that does not pose a serious public danger: violation of moral norms, minor offenses, violation of the rules of behavior in public places; use of narcotic, alcoholic, toxic substances; evasion from socially useful activities.

2. Criminogenic level, expressed in criminally punishable criminal acts. The core of this type of deviant behavior is crime, drug addiction, suicide, alcoholism.

3. Pre-deviant syndrome, which includes a set of symptoms that lead an individual to persistent forms of deviant behavior: family conflicts, affective and aggressive behavior, negative attitude to learning, antisocial behaviors, low level of intelligence»[4]According to the classification provided by Yu.V.Golubev, it is possible to determine the levels of deviations in behavior. In our opinion, that gives us an understanding of the degree of deviations in the behavior of the individual and the forms of his misconduct. We see that each level has its own definiteness and specificity.[5]

In the work on the correction and development of the volitional sphere in adolescents with deviant behavior, the following areas are highlighted:

-normalization and enrichment of teenagers' relationships with the outside world, first of all, with teachers and children's collective;

-compensation for gaps and shortcomings in the overall development of a teenager, strengthening activities in the area that he loves, in which he can achieve good results (compensation in the field of an interesting business, a teenager's passion for sports, technology, music, etc.);

-restoration of positive personality qualities that have received a minor deformation (deviation) in a teenager;

-constant stimulation of positive qualities that have not lost their social significance;

-intensification of positive personality development, formation of leading positive qualities;

-assimilation and accumulation of socially valuable life experience, enrichment of practical activities in various spheres of life;

Accumulation of moral behavior skills, healthy habits and needs based on the organization of students' activities to meet their interests;

-correction as overcoming the negative, that is, the elimination of gaps in the formation of positive and the eradication of negative qualities and bad habits.

According to V.A. Labunskaya, the success of socialization is determined by the dialectical unity of its processes such as adaptation, integration, self-development and self-realization. The imbalance between these components leads to various behavioral deviations [2]. There are common social causes of deviant behavior for all risk groups: 1) social inequality (L.E. Keselman, L.G. Borisova, T.S. Solodova); 2) the moral and ethical factor of deviant behavior (V.I. Ivanov, A.M. Kravchenko, A.B. Purbuev), which is expressed in the low moral and moral level of society, its lack of spirituality; 3) the environment (A.G. Zdravomyslov, G.V. Little), which is neutral about deviant behavior. The primitivization of society justifies various forms of social pathology, ceases not only to fight them, but also to condemn them.

M. Weber refers to the socio-cultural determinants of the post-industrial crisis of personality as a problem of self-determination and freedom.[5]. According to V. Frankl, the source of various behavioral deviations is the lack of meaning of life due to the destruction of old values and traditions and the lack of a culture of reflection that allows you to come to a unique meaning in your own unique way. [6]

Thus, we see that deviant behavior is the result of the influence of society on a person. According to scientific researchers, deviant behavior is the result of need. Also observed: this is a lack of mental, psychological and social education, as a result of which recently there has been an increase in the growth of people with deviations from social norms, which is a problem not only for the individual himself, but also for the whole people, which requires the work of specialists in various fields of activity.

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